

MODERN DNS SERVER SECURITY THREATS

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Abstract: In this article analyzes DNS protocol vulnerabilities, spoofing attacks on DNS systems, DNS cache poisoning attacks, DDOS attacks on DNS servers, DNS trolling attacks, and offers suggestions for using appropriate defenses against each type of attack.

Keywords: DNS Protocol vulnerabilities, DNS Spoofing, Monitoring and auditing DNS, DNS Cache Poisoning, DNS Amplification, DDoS attacks, DNS Tunneling.

The Domain Name System (DNS) is a distributed database that contains information about computers (hosts) connected to the Internet. Most often, this information includes the machine name, IP address, and mail routing data.

As you know, to access hosts on the Internet, 32-bit IP addresses are used that uniquely identify any network computer on this network. However, it is not convenient for users to use IP addresses when accessing hosts. Therefore, a name translation system was created that allows the computer to get the necessary information from the DNS server, whose IP address is stored in the Internet connection settings, if it does not have information about the correspondence of names and IP addresses.

However, despite the critical importance of this system, DNS servers are subject to a variety of threats that can lead to Internet outages, compromise user data, and spread cyber attacks. In this article, we will look at the main security threats to DNS servers and possible measures to prevent them.

1. DNS Protocol vulnerabilities

DNS was developed at a time when security issues were not a priority, which makes it vulnerable to attacks. For example, traditional DNS traffic is not encrypted, which makes it vulnerable to interception and manipulation. Attackers can use man-in-the-middle attacks to spoof DNS responses or intercept information.

In addition, the lack of built-in authentication mechanisms allows attackers to impersonate legitimate DNS servers and change data on the fly.

Security measures:

- **DNS over HTTPS (DoH)** and **DNS over TLS (DoT)**: Encrypting DNS requests and responses helps protect them from interception and manipulation.

- **Regular software updates**: using up-to-date versions of DNS servers with patched vulnerabilities helps protect against most known threats.

2. DNS Spoofing and Record spoofing

DNS Spoofing, or spoofing of DNS records — is an attack in which an attacker changes DNS records or issues fake responses to DNS queries. As a result, the user ends up not on the site that they originally wanted to visit, but on the fake site of the attacker. This can be used to steal passwords, personal data, or distribute malicious software.

This type of attack is particularly dangerous, as users are usually unaware that they have been redirected to a fake site. Visually, the site may look identical to the real one, but all the data entered by the user (for example, usernames and passwords) fall into the hands of intruders.

Security measures:

- **DNSSEC (Domain Name System Security Extensions)**: this technology adds cryptographic signatures to DNS records, which allows you to guarantee the authenticity of responses from DNS servers.

- **Monitoring and auditing DNS records**: regular checking and auditing of records will help you quickly detect suspicious changes.

3. DNS Cache Poisoning

DNS Cache Poisoning is an attack in which an attacker inserts false data into the cache of a DNS resolver. As a result, users accessing this resolver receive fake IP addresses for domains and may be redirected to malicious sites. Cache poisoning can be used for phishing, spreading viruses, or intercepting personal data.

This attack is dangerous because it can affect a large number of users, because the resolver caches data for many requests. If the cache is infected, all subsequent requests to this domain will return false data until the cache is cleared.

Security measures:

- **Using DNSSEC**: Cache protection with signatures ensures that only authentic entries can be stored in the resolver cache.

- **Reduced Cache Lifetime (TTL)**: Reducing the lifetime of cache entries can help eliminate false data faster.

4. DDoS attacks on DNS servers.

DDoS attacks (Distributed Denial of Service) are one of the most serious threats to DNS servers, which can lead to unavailability of Internet resources. In such attacks, attackers send a huge number of requests to the server, creating congestion and blocking the ability to respond to legitimate requests from users. This may lead to unavailability of Internet resources and loss of communication between users and services.

DNS Amplification is a type of DDoS attack in which attackers use DNS resolvers to amplify traffic. The attack works by sending small requests with a fake victim IP address to open DNS resolvers. These resolvers, in turn, send large volume responses to the victim's address, overloading its system.

Security measures:

- **Anycast technologies**: distributing requests across multiple servers around the world reduces the risk of overloading individual servers.

- **Rate Limiting**: Limiting the number of requests from a single source reduces the likelihood of server congestion.

- **Network-level protection:** using network filters and specialized solutions to prevent DDoS attacks.

5. DNS Tunneling

DNS Tunneling is a technique in which DNS queries are used to transmit data through the DNS system, bypassing firewalls and other security systems. Attackers can use this method to secretly exchange data with an infected system, despite existing security measures. This method is also used to extract data from corporate networks or to remotely manage malware.

DNS Tunneling is difficult to detect because DNS queries are usually considered legitimate and rarely blocked. Attackers can inject commands or data into DNS queries and transmit them as encoded data.

Security measures:

- **DNS Traffic Analysis:** Monitoring abnormal DNS traffic behavior can help identify unnatural requests related to tunneling.

- **DNS query filtering:** Using filters to block suspicious queries can reduce the risk of DNS tunneling.

Conclusion

DNS is a critical part of the Internet that affects the availability of most network resources. However, this system is subject to many threats that can lead to serious consequences for users and organizations. DDoS attacks, DNS record spoofing, cache poisoning, and other types of attacks show the importance of strengthening security measures for DNS servers. The introduction of modern technologies such as DNSSEC, traffic encryption, and thorough monitoring are essential measures to protect the DNS infrastructure from ever-changing cyber threats.

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